
A HYPER-SURFACE NORMAL PROJECTION METHOD FOR STEERED-FIBER COMPOSITE OPTIMIZATION

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Abstract. *Composite materials reinforced by long fibers are usually sold as fabrics or plies with constant fiber angle alignment in all their extension, which do not allow attaining the full strength offered by the reinforced fiber. With the increase in precision of robotic arms and new technics for fiber deposition on the matrix, the possibility of creating alignment patterns of fibers with specific curvatures in each application is becoming feasible. Creating curvilinear fiber patterns requires a material design integrated to the mechanical behavior, since the optimum fiber angles will depend on boundary conditions, displacement, stress or natural frequency constraints, or any other wanted performance function. This paper presents a way to parameterize the fiber angles in shell-like structures using finite elements, a set of three polynomials, and a hyper-surface normal projection methodology. The procedure is applied to composite plates and shells to show that this allows good flexibility in the fiber angle orientation, which ease the optimization process.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The parametrization of composite fiber angles maintaining continuity between finite elements has been studied by many researchers. The final structures should have fiber orientations that comply with constraints imposed by the manufacturing process, such as limited final curvatures to avoid wrinkling (Brooks and Martins, 2018).

Brampton *et al.* (2015) proposed a new optimization method to steer fiber composites using the level set method. They proposed the paths of the fibers should be defined by constant level set function values, describing a series of continuous equally spaced fiber paths. The sensitivity of the structural compliance to a change in a level set function of the fiber path is used to guide the optimization of the fiber orientation. The element fiber orientation is set to match the orientation of the constant level set function value path that goes through the element center. This is calculated as perpendicular to the slope of the level set function at the element center.

A similar procedure was proposed by van Campen *et al.* (2011). They proposed to convert variable stiffness laminate designs using lamination parameters into fiber angle designs. The method included a constraint on in-plane curvature, a manufacturing constraint related to automated fiber placement. Arsenyeva and Duddeck (2014) presented the idea of using the level set method to steer the composite fibers using iso-contour lines of an artificial hyper-surface defined over a 2D geometry domain. By modifying this artificial surface, they could control the fiber paths and optimize the design of a composite part for specific needs. Similarly, Arsenyeva *et al.* (2016) used a spline to generate another surface over the finite element mesh and obtaining the fiber angles by tangents of iso-contour lines.

Guimarães *et al.* (2017) propose the use of control points from Lagrange polynomials, which describes a control surface above the finite element mesh of a plate, as design variables, to attain some specific dynamic behavior.

In this paper, three polynomials of 3rd degree are used to generate displacements at nodes of an envelope mesh. Two of these polynomials are used to displace the envelope nodes laterally and the remainder to displace in a normal direction. The coefficients of these polynomials are basic design variables for an optimization process.

2. SELECTED FINITE ELEMENT

In this paper, a square eight-node degenerated finite element is used to perform the structural analysis and obtain both objective functions and the envelope mesh. This element allows good flexibility for curvature variability even with a relatively coarse mesh and is less susceptible to shear and membrane locking.

The concept of degeneration was developed by [5] in the seventies and its origins are based on the idea of reducing a tridimensional element in a plate or shell plane element. Taking as an example a brick element with eight nodes, after the degeneration, the number of nodes is reduced to 4.

2.1. Coordinate system

For the definition of the kinematic relations based on the displacement fields that rule the degenerated finite elements behavior, it is important to define a curvilinear natural coordinate system, a local element coordinate system, and one coordinated system at each node.

The curvilinear natural coordinate system is composed by the coordinates ξ , η e ζ the first two varies between -1 and 1 and follows the curvatures of the element while the last one also varies between -1 and 1. This system has its direction coincident with the thickness and the upper and lower limits corresponds to the physical ones $[-t/2, t/2]$.

For each location in the natural coordinate system, it is possible to define a local Cartesian one. These systems are extremely useful for the evaluation of the local stresses and strains as they are built generating tangent vectors to the natural curvilinear system. The normalized vectors at this coordinate system are defined by Eq. (1) and Eq. (2).

$$\{\mathbf{e}_\xi\} = \frac{\{x_\xi\}}{\|\{x_\xi\}\|}, \quad (1)$$

$$\{\mathbf{e}_\eta\} = \frac{\{x_\eta\}}{\|\{x_\eta\}\|}, \quad (2)$$

where x represents the coordinates x , y , or z . Using equations (1) and (2) is possible to define the normal vector e_3 by the vector product of the precedent vectors.

$$\{\mathbf{e}_3\} = \frac{\{\mathbf{e}_\xi\} \times \{\mathbf{e}_\eta\}}{\|\{x_\eta\}\|} \quad (3)$$

The tangent vectors e_1 and e_2 are built so that the basis e_1, e_2 is close as the e_ξ, e_η basis [6].

$$\{\mathbf{e}_1\} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (\{\mathbf{e}_\alpha\} - \{\mathbf{e}_\beta\}) \quad (4)$$

$$\{e_\beta\} = \frac{\{e_3\} \times \{e_\alpha\}}{\|\{e_3\} \times \{e_\alpha\}\|}, \quad (5)$$

where

$$\{e_\alpha\} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}(\{e_\xi\} + \{e_\eta\})}{\left\| \frac{1}{2}(\{e_\xi\} + \{e_\eta\}) \right\|}, \quad (6)$$

$$\{e_\beta\} = \frac{\{e_3\} \times \{e_\alpha\}}{\|\{e_3\} \times \{e_\alpha\}\|} \quad (7)$$

Finally, there is the nodal coordinate system, which is essential for the determination of the rotational degrees of freedom in plate and shell finite elements. There are many ways to define this coordinate system. This work uses the algorithm suggested by [6]. Letting $\{\hat{X}\}$ denote the unite basis in fiber direction and assuming the global coordinate system vectors as $e_1^0 = \{1 \ 0 \ 0\}^T$, $e_2^0 = \{0 \ 1 \ 0\}^T$, $e_3^0 = \{0 \ 0 \ 1\}^T$ and $a_i = |\hat{X}_i|$, $i = 1,2,3$, assuming initially, $j=1$ then if $a_1 > a_2$, we have $a_3 = a_1$, $e_j=2$. In case $a_2 > a_3$ it is assumed that $j=3$. Based on those assumptions, it is possible to evaluate the vectors at nodal coordinate system as $V_3 = \hat{X}$, $V_2 = \hat{X} \times e_j / \|\hat{X} \times e_j\|$ and $V_1 = e_2^f \times \hat{X}$.

This paper uses the vectors V_3 at each node to generate virtual normal displacements to the shell surface. The projection of the vector e_3 together with the tangent vector of the element coordinate system, e_1 , is then used to define the fiber angle at each Gauss point of the finite element mesh.

3. FIBER ANGLE EVALUATION

3.1. Envelop mesh

The envelop mesh is generated by three equal 3rd-degree polynomials used by [7] and represented by Eq. (8). Two of these polynomials are used to displace the nodes of the envelope mesh laterally and the remaining are used to displace in the normal direction. The coefficients of these polynomials are the design variables for the optimization process.

$$F(x_1, x_2) = c_{10}x_1 + c_{01}x_2 + c_{01}x_1^2 + c_{11}x_1x_2 + c_{02}x_2^2 + c_{30}x_1^3 + x_2^2 + c_{21}x_1^2x_2 + c_{12}x_2^2x_1 + c_{03}x_2^3 \quad (8)$$

Figure 1 shows a finite element mesh for a simple cylinder with the corresponding normal vectors to the mesh. Assuming z as the axial coordinate and y and x as radial, one of the polynomials is taken as a function of x and z , i.e., $F(x, z)$, and the other is taken function of y and z , i.e., $F(y, z)$. The effect of these functions in the final envelope mesh, by arbitrary changes in the coefficients, is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1– Original finite element mesh with the corresponding norm \mathbf{a}_1 vectors.

(a) (b) (c)
Figure 2 – Individual effects of (a) (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) ; (b) $F(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z})$ and (c) combined effects of these two functions in the final envelop hyper-surface.

3.2. Projection of normal vectors of the envelope mesh and fiber angle evaluation

Once the envelope mesh is defined, it is possible to obtain the normal director vectors and their projection on the original finite element plane, as showed by Eq. (9) and presented in Figure 3.

$$\{proj_{e_3^3}\} = \{e_3^{env}\} - \frac{\{e_3^{env}\} \bullet \{e_{ele}^3\}}{\|\{e_3^{env}\}\|} \{e_3^{env}\} \quad (9)$$

Figure 3 – Representation of necessary entities to the fiber angle evaluation at each finite element Gauss point.

After the projection is obtained, it is rotated 90° around the finite element normal vector to ease circular patterns formation.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

In this section, the methodology is tested for a simple one-layered cantilever plate proposed by Pedersen (1991) with uniform pressure over the upper edge. It has $h = 5$ cm in thickness, aspect ratio of $a/b=3$ and $q_0 = 0.115$ MN/m. The material properties are $E_1=181$ GPa, $E_2= E_3=10.3$ GPa, $G_{12}=7.17$ GPa and $\nu_{12}=0.28$.

Figure 4 – Cantilever beam used in the optimization process.

It is used 625 finite elements and a standard particle swarm optimization (PSO) is used to perform the optimization of the fiber orientation by optimizing the polynomial coefficients as described previously.

A population of 500 individuals is used for PSO and the maximum allowed number of iterations is set to 1000, although the convergence occurs near the 600th iteration. The objective function is the non-dimensional compliance, as described by Setoodhe et al. (2006), which is defined by the Eq. (11).

$$C = \frac{1}{2} F^T U \quad (10)$$

$$\bar{C} = \frac{E_2 h b^3 C}{q_0^3 a^5} \quad (11)$$

As reference, a constant stiffness laminate with 0° as fiber angle with the same material properties and boundary conditions is analyzed and resulted in a non-dimensional compliance of $\bar{C}_{con} = 0.0726$. After the optimization, the obtained optimum steered-fiber structure design resulted in the corresponding compliance of $\bar{C}_{var} 0.0299$, that represents a reduction of the final non-dimensional compliance of about 58.74%.

Figure 5 shows the contours of the final level sets for the fiber orientation, the final fiber orientation at the element center (interpolated from the Gauss points for sake of clarity of the figure), and the final hyper-surface that defines the fiber's orientation.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5 – (a) Contour lines for the best design; (b) discretized fibers at element center and (c) corresponding final hyper-surface.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, it is proposed a methodology for steered-fiber composite structures optimization that is a substitute to usual polynomials, interpolated surfaces, and level set methods, reported in the literature. It leads to a considerable improvement in the overall compliance of the optimized structure. Since it is linked to the structure mesh's geometry, it applies to any shell-like structures that develop in space like wind turbine blades, panels, cylinders, spars, or domes.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J.M.J.F. van Campen, C. Kassapoglou, Z. Gürdal, *Design of fiber-steered variable-stiffness laminates based on a given lamination parameters distribution*. 52nd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference. 19th, 4-7, April, 2011, Denver, Colorado. AIAA 2011-1894. (2011) doi:10.2514/6.2011-1894
- [2] A.L. Ansenyeva, F. Duddeck. *Iso-contour method for optimization of steered-fiber composites*. Proceedings of the 10th ASMO UK Conference Engineering Design Optimization, page 23, June (2014).
- [3] T.A.M. Guimarães, D.A. Pereira, D.A. Rade. *Dynamic behavior and optimization of tow steered composite plates*. Proceedings of DINAME 2017, Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering, Springer, Cham, 2019.
- [4] A.L. Ansenyeva, F. Duddeck. *Optimization of fiber-steered composites by using the iso-contour method with maximum curvature constraint*. ECCM17 - 17th European Conference on Composite Materials, Munich, Germany, 26-30th June. (2016).
- [5] S. Ahmad, B.M. Irons, O.C. Zienkiewicz. *Analysis of thick and thin shell structures by curved finite elements*. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 2(3), 419-451. (1970)
- [6] T.J. Hughes. The C^o- Approach to Curved Structural Elements. In: *The finite element method: Linear static and dynamic finite element analysis* (pp. 385-387). New York: Dover Publication. (2007).
- [7] T. Igarashi, S. Honda, Y. Narita. *Multi-objective Optimization of Fibrous Composite Reinforced by Curvilinear Fibers*. The Proceedings of the Dynamics & Design Conference, 2011(1).
- [8] P. Pedersen. *On Thickness and Orientational Design with Orthotropic Materials*. *Structural Optimization*, V.3, No. 2, (1991), pp. 69–78. doi:10.1007/bf01743275.
- [9] S. Setoodeh, M.M. Abdalla, Z. Gürdal. *Design of Variable–Stiffness Laminates Using Lamination Parameters*. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol.37, No. 4-5, pp.301–309. (2006).

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